

Importance of mother tongue science in primary grades

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ANNOTATION: (content of the article) - the article talks about the importance, necessity, purpose and tasks of mother tongue science in 1-2 grades and its connection with other subjects and the essence of teaching.

KEY WORDS: mother tongue, young generation, importance, future, student, pedagogue continuous, competence, science, knowledge, skill, qualification.

It is known that every subject taught to students in schools is important in the development of the young generation as a person who is perfect, knowledgeable, able to find his place in life, full of self-confidence, and useful to society. , elementary school students of the first and second grade, i.e. the younger generation, serves as an important foundation for the younger generations who have just taken their first steps on the threshold of knowledge . We can see the importance of science. Today, the attention paid to the education system, the wide opportunities created in this field and the new innovations impose a huge responsibility not only on the student, but also on every pedagogue. Educators consider the process of forming the creative maturity of each young generation to be mentally mature , physically mature, and mentally mature. Indeed, among the subjects taught in the 1st and 2nd grades of the primary school, the subject of the mother tongue occupies an important place . Without knowing the subject of the mother tongue well, without understanding the rules of sentences and words, mastering the rest of the subjects is difficult for every student. We can say that it will definitely cause difficulties for students. The mother tongue of each people is the language of the nation . It consists of words and concepts that tell about national values, preserved customs, and traditions. Mother tongue is the soul of this nation. The language is a national symbol. Preservation and development of the language, preservation of the essence of the language means the rise of the nation . We all know that in the old educational system, the subject of the mother tongue was not taught for the 1st and 2nd grades. the young generation who have not reached the threshold of

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school want to learn not only their mother tongue, but also a foreign language as soon as possible. These aspects require every teacher to work more on himself.

We can cite many of our expert pedagogues as an example of achievements in the field of education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan . For example, in the results of a number of scientific researches, such as Karimova Kasimova's "methodology of mother tongue teaching", Q. Husanboyev 's "literature as a factor of spirituality and independent opinion formation", U. Normatov's "Actual problems of mother tongue teaching", the essence of mother tongue to the young generation collected information about. There is a saying among the people: what you seek, you will find an opportunity. Among our research, we used the study guides of our teachers above.

In all mother tongue classes, students spend time repeating their previous lessons in order to improve their knowledge and ability to improve their independent thoughts and ideas. In our time, the lessons are such that the student should not become a listener, and the teacher should not be exposed. at the same time it helps to strengthen. It is known that every lesson strengthened in the subject of the mother tongue is an important basis for the remaining subjects of the student. The current BU, in turn, is used to determine and take into account the knowledge acquired in the subject of the mother tongue. It is important to improve oral and written speech. The continuity of the actions from the very beginning will continue. because they are based on the foundations of literacy and moral education. That is why they should not get tired of the sacred word "LESSON" from the very beginning, that is, from the 1st or 2nd grade. In the 1st and 2nd grades, the subject of the mother tongue is especially distinguished. Through the lessons of the mother tongue, the student's literacy develops. He learns to write, write correctly and fluently without spelling mistakes, and how to use adverbs. This subject It is important for students to learn other subjects well later. First of all, it is necessary to be able to properly organize the science of the mother tongue in learning a number of features of students, such as increasing vocabulary, teaching them to think broadly, improve their oral and written speech in one form, and increase their consciousness. Teaching to think and think is one of the main tasks of the mother tongue science. it is very important that it is placed on the basis of That's why the main goal of teaching the language is to form creative thinking and independent thoughts of the young generation, to express their thoughts in written and oral form in a free and effective meaningful, logical way. Teaching to master is also aimed at expanding their horizons, educating them in the spirit of love for our motherland, the rich spirituality

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left by our ancestors, and our national traditions. In the 1st and 2nd grades, the state education standard requires age-related and necessary knowledge. The students of the 1st grade must be able to express their opinion in writing, independently. able to connect words to form sentences, create short text in sentences, write two types of 15-20 word dictation, know punctuation marks, use word spacing and the indicated the requirements for being able to visualize independently from the pictures are set. 2nd grade students in the subject of mother tongue; to express his opinion more widely independently, to be able to write a dictation of 35-40 words, to know all three forms of dictation, to be able to independently compose and write a text consisting of 4 to 5 sentences, and to pronounce it correctly. From this we can see that the gradual teaching of the subject of the native language and the acquisition of knowledge in terms of age ensure the continuity of this subject.

COMPETENCY is the ability to apply the acquired theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies in solving practical and theoretical problems encountered in everyday life. According to the level of knowledge acquired by each student in terms of age, according to his practical skills, according to the qualification activity, he can embody the processes of competence. means that they can prove their knowledge, and this forms self-confidence in students, develops students' thinking, and allows them to express themselves. It is necessary for the students to retain the necessary knowledge and skills with a deep understanding of their importance. Only then will the students become highly literate individuals in the future.

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